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Introduction. Milk and dairy products contain high-quality protein, calcium and vitamins. Milk contains more than 250 different substances, including 120 different fatty acids, 25 different amino acids, 30 different mineral substances, 23 different vitamins, as well as 4 different milk sugars. In addition, milk contains various pigments, enzymes, phosphatides and other substances.

Cow's milk is the most consumed milk according to the level of industrial processing and consumption by the population.

Cow's milk contains all the nutrients necessary for the growth and development of a young organism: proteins, fats, carbohydrates and minerals in an easily digestible form.

When one liter of cow's milk is consumed, a person's daily energy requirement for energy is satisfied by 25%, protein requirement - 61%, fat requirement -

METHODS OF EFFICIENT USE OF DAIRY COWS

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ABSTRACT

The article provides information on effective methods of using purebred cattle, taking into account the breed and age of dairy cows, determining lactation periods, and producing maximum milk in order to produce high-quality milk products in cattle breeding.

100%, calcium requirement - 100-150%, phosphorus requirement - 112%.

It contains an average of 12.5-13% dry matter; of which there are 3.8% fat, 3.3% protein, 4.8% lactose and about 1% macro and microelements. 95-98% of the nutrients contained in milk are digested by the human body. The chemical composition of cow's milk, the level of satiety, the health of animals during the lactation period varies under the influence of feeding and keeping conditions and other factors.

The coefficient of lactation stagnation is 97-99% when milk production is uniform in high-yielding cows, and 75-78% in low-yielding cows that quickly reduce their milk.

In cows with uniform milk production, this indicator is 70% and more, and in low-yielding cows it is 50% and below.

Most of the milk produced in our republic is milked from cows. Therefore, cattle breeding plays an important role in

meeting the needs of the population for milk and dairy products.

The purpose of the study. In order to produce high-quality dairy products in cattle breeding, it is necessary to feed dairy cows with nutritious food, take into account their breed and age, determine lactation periods and produce maximum milk.

Object of the research and learning method. Dairy cattle, Black-and-white breed, red-desert breed, lactation, daily milk yield, average milk yield, milk fat content. Zootechnical, biological and analytical methods were used.

Research and analytical results. The most milk-producing period of dairy cows corresponds to the period of 7-8 years of age. The main reason for the increase of the milk produced during lactation by this age is that the mammary glands of cows are fully developed by this period, the body is fully grown, and the organs and tissues are

fully formed. When cows are 7-8 years old, their live weight reaches the highest level. At this age, their internal organs and mammary glands are fully developed. because the production of milk depends on the body and live weight of the cows.

Depending on the maturity of cattle of different breeds, their milk yield differs. The milk yield of the first-born cows in late maturing cattle breeds is 70% of the milk yield of middle-aged cows. This indicator corresponds to 80% in fast breeding breeds. This condition is also observed in cows belonging to the same breed. Young bulls, heifers and cows fed in good conditions and at a high level of nutrition quickly reach a high level of productivity.

The milk yield of experimental cows during lactation was determined by means of control milking every 10 days.

Table 1

Milk yield of experimental cows.

№	Indicators	Measuring unit	Black-and-white	Red-desert
1	The period of lactation	day	267	249
2	Milk productivity during the lactation	kg	2448	2205
3	The amount of fat in the milk	%	3,8	3,8

Duration of the lactation period was 267 days in the first group, and 249 days in the second group. The amount of milk obtained from 1 cow during lactation in the first group was 2448 kg, and in the second group it was 2205 kg.

Cows of group I gave 243 kg more milk than cows of group II during lactation.

The average amount of fat in the milk of cows in both groups was 3.8%.

Table 2

The amount of milk received by the months of lactation, kg

Months	Groups			
	Black-and-white		Red-desert	
	Daily	Monthly	Daily	Monthly
March	10,5	315	9,6	288
April	12	360	11	330
May	14	420	12,8	384

June	11,5	345	10,6	318
July	8,8	264	8,2	246
August	7,5	225	6,6	198
September	6,2	186	5,7	171
October	6,1	183	5	150
November	5	150	4	120
Total	9,1	2448	8,2	2205

The data in the table show that the milk yield of cows increased in both groups during the first 1-3 months of lactation. From 4 months, the daily and monthly milk yield of cows began to decrease, and from 6 months, it decreased sharply. Because from the 6th month of lactation, the third ten days of the cow's period begins, and the child in the mother's womb grows and develops rapidly.

Conclusion. Thus, taking into account the natural and economic conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the number of breeding cattle, there are all opportunities to conduct zootechnical research.

When using cattle for the production of milk and meat, special attention should be paid to its biological properties and a scientific approach. Then, it becomes possible to achieve high economic efficiency in production.

The scientific significance of the results of the research is that in the case of providing the population with basic food products, that is, milk and milk products, the increase in the production of livestock products is achieved in the case of taking into account the consumption demand and the increase in income.

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